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DETERMINATION OF PESTICIDE RESIDUES FROM THE LOCAL GRAPES VARIETY MERLO AND CABERNET SAUVIGNON

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ANNOTATION

This study was conducted to investigate the pesticide residue concentrations from the grape consumption in Azerbaijan. A total of samples of grapes variety Merlo and Cabernet sauvignon were collected from the Ganja area in 2019. The pesticide residues were analyzed by gas-liquid chromatography. A total of 3 different pesticide residues were found and 2 residues exceeded MRLs. The most frequently detected pesticide residues were acetamiprid, metalaxyl and dimetomorph.

Key words: determination, pesticide, grapes, MRLs.

Introduction

Pesticides are essential tools to increase agricultural productivity and cultivation convenience. Pesticides are involved in a wide range of organic micro pollutants that have negative environmental effects. Several groups of pesticides have specific mechanism of contamination of living organisms, which is why generalization is difficult [1]. The use of pesticides in agriculture is a subcategory of the largest group of manufactured compounds used in the present world [2, 3]. The transfer of pesticides sourced from agricultural land may be harmful to terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. [3]. Samples for analyse are grapes variety Merlo and Cabernet sauvignon were collected from the area. Grapes may contain toxic residual pesticides due to the use of pesticides during the production process of agricultural products. Pesticide residues in agricultural products are usually monitored with reference to maximum residue limits (MRLs), which represent the highest concentration of pesticide residues that is legally permitted or accepted in food commodities after the use of pesticides [4].

Data analysis and processing

The objects of research are two grape varieties Merlo and Cabernet sauvignon. Instrumental work to determine the residual amounts of pesticides in the specified material were performed in the People's Reference Laboratory of the Azerbaijan Institute of Food Safety. In the objects under study, the content of nitrogen-containing fungicide preparations containing a phenyl residue using the example of acrobat and ridomil gold was determined by gas chromatography (GC) according to approved methods as well as the mospilan insecticide. The active ingredients of these pesticides in

the composition of acrobat-dimetamorph in the composition of ridomil gold - mancozeb and metalaxil in the composition of mospilan - asetamiprid.

Acetamiprid is a nicotine-like substance and reacts to the body in a similar way as nicotine. Nicotine is a natural insecticide of which many man-made insecticides are derivatives. Acetamiprid is a nicotinic agonist that reacts with nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nACh-R). Acetamiprid is an α -chloro-N-heteroaromatic compound [4]. It is a neonicotinoid with a chloropyridinyl group and it is comparable to other neonicotinoids such as imidacloprid, nitenpyram and thiacloprid. These substances all have a 6-chloro-3-pyridine methyl group but differ in the nitroguanidine, nitromethylene, or cyanoamidine substituent on an acyclic or cyclic moiety [5].

Chemical structure of acetamiprid:

Dimethomorph, a cinnamic acid derivative, is a member of the morpholine group of fungicides and consists of a mixture of the Z and E isomers in approximately equal proportions. Its mode of action is through the disruption of fungal cell wall formation.

Chemical structure of dimetomorph:

Metalaxyl is an acylalanine fungicide with systemic function. Its chemical name is methyl N-(methoxyacetyl)-N-(2,6-xyllyl)-DL-alaninate. It can be used to control Pythium in a number of fruits and vegetable crops, and Phytophthora in peas.

The analysis of samples according to the presented methods allows for a qualitative analysis of these fungicides and a quantitative determination of the insecticide residue in the grapes (Fantke et al., 2012). A modified, efficient, and sensitive acetate-buffered QuEChERS extraction method was developed for the quantitative study of 3 commonly applied multiclass pesticides on grapes. Samples were extracted with acidified acetonitrile, buffered with acetate salt. To minimize the matrix interferences, clean-up of the rehydrated samples was optimized by comparison with different sorbents (alumina, silica gel, florisil, primary secondary amine (PSA), and chitosan). The method validation parameters were evaluated as per European Union (EU) guidelines (SANTE/12682/2019). For 3 pesticides, % recovery of 69 to 121.8% with an associated precision (RSD $\leq$ 20%) was achieved at the fortification levels that were 0.5 to 2 times of European Union maximum residue limits (EU-MRLs) [5]. The validated method was successfully employed for the analysis of grapes variety Merlo and Cabernet sauvignon samples (n=20) collected from Ganja region of Azerbaijan. The most frequently detected residues were dimetomorph, metalaxyl and acetamiprid. The concentration of all the detected pesticides in real samples was below the EU-MRLs.

400 pesticide standards used to analyze pesticide residues were purchased by Accustandard (New Haven, CT, USA). For the extraction of pesticide residues, acetonitrile, acetone, dichloromethane and n-hexane used in this experiment were purchase with HPLC grade reagents (Muskegon, MI, USA). These analyzes were performed on LCMS MS 8045. The sample is homogenized. After homogenization we add a part to the centrifuge tube. Due to the presence of 80% water in the composition, we do not add water. Add 10 ml of acetonitrile to the sample. Close the centrifuge and turn it on for one minute. 4g of MgSO₄, 1g of NaCl, 1 g of trinitrate citrate dihydrate, 0.5 g of disodium hydrocitrate sesquigurate buffer-salt mixture were added to the resulting suspension. Vortex vigorously for one minute. After that stir in a centrifuge for five minutes. Add 6 ml of an aliquot of acetonitrileic phase to the resulting solution. We move it in the centrifuge. The solution is isolated and from the pure extract we take 1 ml. To increase the acidity add 10 μ l of formic acid solution. Switch to avto sample mode and start chromatographic analysis. Chromatographic separation was performed on a Capcell Core C18 column (4.6 mm $\times$ 100 mm, 2.7 μ m particle size, Osaka Soda, Osaka, Japan).

Figure 1. Chromatogram graph for the determination of acetamiprid in a sample of variety Cabernet sauvignon from a vineyard on the territory of Ganja by gas-liquid chromatography

HPLC conditions consisted of mobile phase A (5% acetonitrile in water), mobile phase B (20% methanol/80% acetonitrile, v/v), 10 µL injection volume, 1.0 mL/min flow rate and 40 °C oven temperature. UV absorbance was monitored at 220 nm and 250 nm. The gradient program was as follows: initial (90% A/10% B), 0–13 min (10–80% B), 13–16 min (20% A), 16–16.1 min (20–90% A) and 16.1–20 min (90% A/10% B) [5]. As a result dimetamorph and metalaxyl were found in the Merlo grape variety, acetamiprid and metalaxyl were found in the Cabernet sauvignon grape variety from the vineyard in the Ganja region .Below are the chromatograms for the detection of the listed compounds.

Figure 2. Chromatogram graph for the determination of metalaxyl in a sample of variety Cabernet sauvignon from a vineyard on the territory of Ganja by gas-liquid chromatography

Figure 3. Chromatogram graph for the determination of dimetomorph in a sample of variety Merlo from a vineyard on the territory of Ganja by gas-liquid chromatography

Figure 4. Chromatogram graph for the determination of metalaxyl in a sample of variety Merlo from a vineyard on the territory of Ganja by gas-liquid chromatography

The amount of acetamiprid was 8.55 ppb, the amount of metalaxyl was 92.528 ppb in tabrizi variety using quantitative analysis. The amount of dimetomorph in the madrasa variety by quantitative analysis is 14.05 ppb, the amount of metalaxyl was 92.628 ppb . Below is a list of grape samples that should be used to determine pesticides:

pesticides	variety	amount of pesticides
metalaxyl	Cabernet sauvignon	92.528 ppb
dimetamorph	Merlo	14.05 ppb
acetamiprid	Cabernet sauvignon	8.55 ppb
metalaxyl	Merlo	92.628 ppb

Conclusion

In the paper two grape varieties - madrasa, and tabrizi from the grape sites of the Ganja-Gazakh zone of Azerbaijan are studied, some pesticides are determined in the considered samples. Analysis of the quantitative determination of pesticides are carried out in the considered samples.

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